

EFFECTS OF NANOCCLAYS AND WOOD FLOUR ON THE PERFORMANCE OF POLYURETHANE FOAMS

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Keywords: *cellular foams, polyurethane, nanoclay, wood flour, characterization*

1 Introduction

The use of sandwich composite structures in automotive, aerospace, and marine industries is constantly increasing due to their high strength to weight ratios which leads to weight reductions of components, as well as lower fuel consumption during service. Also, improved levels of crashworthiness are a possibility in such materials, due to their capability of absorbing large amount of energy in the event of collision occurring while in use. The concept of reinforcing polymers with fillers derived from natural sources has attracted increasing interest due to heightened environmental regulations. Due to the significant effect that nanoclay has on polymeric foam core materials, it is imperative to perform a comparative study and analysis of commonly used clays in polyurethane (PU) foams. Therefore, studies on the cell structure and properties of PU containing various montmorillonite nanoclays are very important. Our current focus is on developing modified closed cell polyurethane foam used as core material in sandwich construction. Two materials being considered as fillers here are nanoclay and wood flour. Polyurethane foams with nanoclay as fillers have shown to have improved mechanical and thermal behavior [1-10]. Advantages of wood polymer composites include low cost, low density, low CO₂ emission, biodegradability and renewable [11-13]. While wood flour has been primarily used with thermoplastic polymers, it is worthwhile to investigate their influence on the morphology and performance of polyurethane foams. Hence, in this study, we have investigated the influence of three different types of nanoclay and wood flour on the morphology, thermal and mechanical performance of closed cell polyurethane foams. Three organically-modified nanoclays (Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, and Nanomer[®] I.28E) and maple

wood flour were the fillers of choice. Microstructure of foams obtained from SEM examined the effects of nanoclay and wood flour particles on cell shape, size, and wall thickness. Moisture absorption studies were performed to examine whether or not the presence of fillers affects moisture uptake of foams. The effects of montmorillonite nanoclays and wood flour on the thermal stability of foams were evaluated through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Thermo-mechanical properties were evaluated through dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) studies to investigate the effects of fillers on viscoelastic nature of foams. In terms of mechanical characterization, three point bend flexure testing was done to investigate the effects of fillers on the stiffness and strength of foams. Additionally, quasi-static compression was performed to evaluate compressive modulus and strength of foams.

2. Experimental

Morphological, thermal, viscoelastic and mechanical performance of closed cell polyurethane foam were studied. The foam material is a two-part system obtained from Utah foam products. Part-A is a diphenylmethane diisocyanate and Part-B is a polyol that employs blowing and curing agents. Nominal density of foam is 80kg/m³. Mix ratio of part A and B is 52:48 by weight. Organically-modified montmorillonite nanoclays used in this study were Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B supplied by Southern Clay Products, and Nanomer[®] I.28E purchased from Nancor. In addition, maple wood flour supplied by American Wood Fibers Corp with particle size of 75-125 μm was used.

Manufacturing of neat polyurethane foam was achieved by reacting desired amount of the two-part system, and casting of foam to obtain desired dimensions. Manufacturing of nanophased and wood flour foam composites was carried out in a five step

process. First, as received nanoclays and wood flour were dried in a vacuum oven. Next, pre-calculated amounts of clays and wood flour were taken so that composites would contain 0.5 and 2.5 percentage of loading by weight, respectively. These particles were then mixed with less reactive and less viscous part-A of the polyurethane system by ultrasonic cavitation for 30 minutes at an amplitude of 30%. Then, the modified part-A was mixed with part-B by using a mechanical stirrer operating at about 2500 rpm for about 45 seconds. Finally, the mixture was poured in a preheated aluminum rectangular mold and kept at ambient temperature for curing. After about 24 hours, the cast foam was demolded and samples were cut for morphological, mechanical, thermo-mechanical, and thermal analysis.

Dynamic mechanical (DMA), flexure, quasi-static compression, thermogravimetric (TGA), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies were carried out.

3. Results

3.1 Morphological Analysis

To investigate the effect of the infusion of nanoclay and wood flour on the microstructure of polyurethane foams, SEM analyses were carried out on neat, nanophased, and wood flour foam samples. Figure 1 (a-e) shows the scanning electron micrographs of a) neat PU, b) Cloisite[®] 10A, c) Cloisite[®] 30B, d) Nanomer[®] I.28E, and e) wood flour reinforced foams respectively. As seen in the micrographs, the cell edges and walls are distinctly visible with almost uniform cell structures throughout the micrograph. Shapes of the cells are primarily spherical for foams, with the exception of wood flour reinforced foams which appear to be more elliptical. The cells also are smaller in size in comparison to neat foam, which indicates the cell density increased with the addition of nanoclay and wood flour particles. Cell sizes averaged 315 μm , 208 μm , 218 μm , 232 μm , and 256 μm for neat, Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, Nanomer[®] I.28E, and wood flour foams respectively. The reason for cell size reduction can be attributed to the particles acting as nucleating agents, reducing gas diffusivity in the polyurethane. Additionally, cell wall thicknesses were calculated for neat and composite foams respectively at higher magnifications.

3.2 Thermo Gravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Figure 2 shows the weight loss vs. temperature curves for organophilic clays and wood flour particles. From the TGA, it is evident that of the fillers used for this investigation that wood flour isn't as thermally stable as the organophilic clays. This is expected due to the fact wood flour is an organic material; therefore one of its characteristics is low thermal stability due to its cyclic structure. Investigating the organophilic clays over the temperature range studied, it can be seen that the Cloisite[®] 30B is most thermally stable, followed by Nanomer[®] I.28E, and then the Cloisite[®] 10A. These findings indicate that the surface modification of the clays plays a key role in their thermal stability. From the curves, it is seen that the degradation of wood flour occurs in one major event (occurring at approximately 350 °C), whereas degradation of nanoclays occur in a multi-step process. In terms of nanoclays, degradation of Cloisite[®] 10A clays occur at approximately 210, 283, and 256 °C. Degradation of Cloisite[®] 30B occur at approximately 273 and 397 °C, and at 237, 316, and 419 °C for Nanomer[®] I.28E clays. First decomposition step is due to absorbed cations. For higher temperatures(500-700 °C), dehydroxylation of the aluminosilicate is observed.

Figure 3 shows the weight loss vs. temperature curves of neat, nanophased, and wood flour infused PU foam samples. It is observed from the figure that decomposition behaviors of all foams are in the form of a two-step degradation process, therefore decomposition temperatures reported correspond to onset decomposition (T_d) and 50% decomposition (T_{50}) of the material, as well as residue at 800 °C. It was observed that the presence of nanoclays and wood flour increased the onset thermal degradation foams 2-5 °C in comparison to neat foams. Also, at 50% decomposition of material it is observed that temperatures were higher 1-3°C for composite, with the highest increase observed in foams containing Cloisite nanoclays. Residue amounts left after testing were found to be 12.5%, 19.9%, 15.1%, 13.8%, and 13.3% for neat PU, 10A/PU, 30B/PU, WF/PU, and I.28E/PU foams, respectively. The increased residual amounts of composite foams are believed to due to improved bonding of cells in their structure; therefore, more energy is required for

decomposition of such foams. The foams reinforced with Nanomer[®] I.28E nanoclay and wood flour shows comparable thermal stability. However, the performance of Cloisite clays showed the greatest thermal stabilities, with the Cloisite[®] 30B showing the most promising results. This is believed to be due to the formation of stable ether linkages due to interaction between the two adjacent –OH groups.

3.3 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

The viscoelastic behavior of neat, nanophased, and wood flour foams obtained from DMA test are represented in terms of variation of storage modulus (E' , elastic response), loss modulus (E'' , viscous response), and $\tan \delta$ with temperatures are shown in Figures 4-6. The storage modulus is related to a material's stiffness, the loss modulus to a material's damping or energy dissipation capabilities, and the temperature corresponding to the peak value of the $\tan \delta$ curve is designated as the glass transition temperature, T_g . From Figure 4, it is seen that the storage modulus increased with the addition of nanoclays and wood flour particles. Average storage modulus values for neat, 0.5% 10A, 0.5% 30B, 0.0% I.28E nanoclay and 2.5%WF reinforced polyurethane foams were 64.1, 91.5, 86.1, 81.3 and 74.3 MPa respectively showing improvements in the range of 16-43%. In comparing only the composite foams, the greatest enhancements were observed with foams reinforced with Cloisite[®] 10A nanoclays; the least amount of influence was found in wood flour reinforced foams. The improved storage modulus values of composite foams are due to the restricted movement of polymer chains, which indicates that the presence of clays and wood flour makes foams stiffer. The increased cell density is a possible explanation for increased storage modulus values. The presence of nanoclay and wood flour led to enhancements in loss modulus values of foams, Figure 5. Average loss modulus values for neat, 0.5% 10A, 0.5% 30B, 0.0% I.28E nanoclay and 2.5%WF reinforced polyurethane foams were 5.17, 7.45, 7.20, 7.16 and 6.54 MPa respectively showing improvements in the range of 27-44%. The greatest enhancements were shown in Cloisite[®] 10A reinforced foams. From the $\tan \delta$ curves, shown in Figure 6, the presence of the clays and wood flour didn't seem to alter the T_g 's of foams, due to the fact that there was no considerable shifts in the peak positions of the peaks. However, and increase in the

area under the $\tan \delta$ curve indicates that nanoclay and wood flour enhances the damping characteristics of foams.

3.4 Flexural Analysis

Flexure stress-strain curves for neat and composite foams are depicted in Figure 7. It can be observed from the curves that the addition of clays and wood flour leads to enhancements in flexure modulus and strength in comparison to neat foams. The greatest improvements in modulus was observed with foams reinforced with nanoclays, with 57%, 38%, 32% for Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, and Nanomer[®] I.28E respectively, followed by a 24% improvement for foams containing wood flour. The increases in modulus can be attributed to the fact the presence of particles yields foams which are much more stiff and brittle. An indication of this is reflected in the lower strain at peak load values. Additionally, from the curves it can be seen that neat foams failed at a lower loading in comparison to composite foams. Although composite foams were able to withstand higher loadings, their failure occurred abruptly under the loading point compared to that of neat foams. This type of immediate failure is attributed to their brittleness. Enhancements in flexure strength were 39%, 36%, 33%, and 30%, for Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, Nanomer[®] I.28E, and wood flour composite foams. The increase in flexural strength is believed to be due to the presence of the particles delaying crack initiation and growth at early loading stages, which in turn results in higher peak loads for composite foams in comparison to neat foams.

3.6 Quasi-Static Compression Analysis

Compressive stress-strain curves for the neat, nanophased and wood flour reinforced polyurethane foams are shown in Figure 8. The curves show three stages of deformation: initial linear-elastic behavior, stress plateau region, and finally, densification. The linear-elastic region is described as the bending of cells walls in elastic behavior. This region is where the modulus is calculated by taking the slope of the curve. The stress plateau is associated with the collapsing of cell walls at nearly constant stress. The intersection of point between the initial slope and the plateau slope is used to calculate the compressive strength. When the cells have collapsed and began to touch each other, a rapid rise occurs in the stress-strain curve, which is called densification. It is

observed that addition of nanoclays and wood flour leads to improvements in compressive modulus and strength of foams. Compressive modulus was 13.8 MPa for neat foams, whereas it was 22.2 MPa, 21.4 MPa, 18.2 MPa, and 17.2 MPa for Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, Nanomer I.28E, and wood flour foams, respectively. Average peak stresses of samples before failure were 0.54 MPa, 1.18 MPa, 0.80 MPa, 0.79 MPa, and 0.74 for neat, Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, Nanomer I.28E, and wood flour foams, respectively. Additionally, the curves for composite foams showed lower strains in the densification region, which is directly due to the brittle nature due to particle incorporation. Figure 9 shows scanning electron micrographs of samples subjected to quasi-static compression. It is observed that most of the cells for neat foams seems to have suffered complete deformation, as there appear to be much more cell rupturing. However, cells of composite foams appear to offer much more resistance, as there appears to be much uniform cells intact after testing. This behavior can be attributed to the cells walls of composite foams being thicker, and therefore the applied load required to deform is much greater.

4. Summary

In this study, effects of modification of polyurethane foam with Cloisite[®] 10A, Cloisite[®] 30B, Nanomer[®] I.28E nanoclays and maple wood flour on the morphological, thermal, thermomechanical, and mechanical characteristics were studied. Results of microstructure, viscoelastic, thermal and mechanical analysis conducted on neat, nanophased, and wood flour polyurethane foams are summarized as follows:

- SEM micrographs showed a decrease in overall cell size, which indicates increased cell density compared to neat foams. Smallest average cell sizes were observed for foams containing Cloisite[®] 10A and Cloisite[®] 30B nanoclays, followed by Nanomer[®] I.28E nanoclays, and the wood flour.
- Moisture absorption studies showed that nanoclays reduced the susceptibility of foams to observe moisture. However, significant moisture uptake was observed for WF/PU foams.

- An increase in onset thermal degradation temperatures of $\sim 2 - 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ was observed for composite foams in comparison to neat foams. Also an increase of $\sim 1 - 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ was observed for composite foams at 50% decomposition of foams for composite foams when compared to neat foams. The residual amounts left after the TGA experiments were found to be 12.5% for neat foams, whereas they were found to be 15.1%, 19.9%, 13.8%, and 13.3% for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams, respectively.
- Storage modulus was increased by $\sim 43\%$, 43%, 27%, and 16% for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams when compared to neat foams. Similarly, loss modulus was increased by $\sim 44\%$, 39%, 39%, and 27% for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams in comparison to neat foams. No significant effects were observed on T_g 's, however the area under the $\tan \delta$ curves indicated enhanced damping characteristics of composite foams
- Flexure modulus increased by $\sim 57\%$, 38%, 32%, and 24% for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams over neat foams. Flexural strength increased by $\sim 39\%$, 36%, 33%, 30%, for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams in comparison to neat foams.
- Compressive modulus increased by $\sim 61\%$, 55%, 32%, and 27% for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams when compared to neat foams. Compressive strength increased by $\sim 118\%$, 48%, 46%, and 37% for 10A/PU, 30B/PU, I.28E/PU, and WF/PU foams over neat foams.

Acknowledgements

Authors would like to thank Office of Naval Research (grant # N00014-08-1-0665) and NSF-EPSCoR (grant # EPS-1158862) for funding this work. Second author would also like to thank Alabama Commission on Higher Education for providing graduate research scholar fellowship.

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Fig. 1. Scanning Electron Micrographs (x160) of (a) neat PU, (b) 10A/PU, (c) 30B/PU, (d) I.28E/PU, and (e) WF/PU

Fig. 2. TGA curves of organophilic clays and wood flour particles.

Fig.3. TGA curves for neat, nanophased and wood flour foams.

Fig. 4. Storage modulus vs. temperature curves for neat, nanophased, and wood flour foams.

Fig. 5. Loss modulus vs. temperature curves for neat, nanophased, and wood flour foams.

Fig. 6. Tan delta vs. temperature curves for neat, nanophased, and composite foams.

Figure 7. Flexural response of neat, nanophased, and wood flour foams.

Fig. 8. Compressive response of 1 neat, nanophased, and wood flour foams.

Fig. 9. SEM (x160) micrographs of post-static compression samples of (a) Neat PU (b) 10A/PU, (c) 30B/PU, (d) I.28E/PU, and (e) WF/PU